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Research Article

**A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY ON PNEUMONIA IN THE
PATIENTS OF DIABETES MELLITUS****¹Dr Adil Muhammad, ²Dr Jevaria Tariq, ³Dr Muhammad Tanseer Sibtain Raza**¹Services Hospital Lahore²Allied / DHQ Hospital Faisalabad³DHQ Hospital Narowal**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: Pneumonia is common coexistent complication of DM (Diabetes Mellitus). Pneumonia is much important reason of high rate of morbidity as well as mortality in these patients. The objective of this research work is to examine clinical presentation of pneumonia in the patients of Diabetes Mellitus, to examine the frequent etiological agents responsible for pneumonia in the patients of Diabetes Mellitus and to examine the pneumonia's outcome in these patients.

Methodology: 40 patients of Diabetes Mellitus with pneumonia underwent study in radiological, pathological and clinical aspects.

Results: Male gender and uncontrolled diabetes mellitus had much high incidence of pneumonia related with Diabetes Mellitus. Most of the patients were also present with tuberculosis. Cough and high temperature were the common complaints.

Conclusion: Adverse control of diabetes mellitus, availability of the comorbid complications and risk of bacteremia & septicemia significantly influenced Mortality, in selected patients. Better glycemic control has the ability to decrease the chances of other infections and better outcome.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Mortality, Pneumonia, Infections, Glycemic, Cough, Etiological, Tuberculosis.

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INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes Mellitus is one of the causes of high rate of morbidity and mortality in the developing as well as developed countries. IDF has estimated that it will cross 435 million population by the year of 2030 [1]. High prevalence of Diabetes Mellitus in Pakistan is because of the sedentary life-style, fatness, stress, HTN, low involvement in physical activities and utilization of rough food. Increase in the economic development will rise the prevalence of Diabetes Mellitus in this region higher than the estimation [1]. Productivity loss because of diabetes and complication specific with Diabetes Mellitus aggravate the economic issue [1]. There is high incidence of Diabetes Mellitus in Asia as compared to other regions [2]. The prevalence of pneumonia, UTI (Urinary Tract Infection) and infection of skin are the common complications faced by patients of diabetes. Most common organisms are gram-negative organisms, myco-bacterium tuberculosis and *S. aureus* [3]. Most common underlying disease is Diabetes Mellitus for the patients present with community-acquired pneumonia [4]. There is strong association of magnitude as well as duration of hyperglycemia with the severity of micro-vascular & neurologic problem [5].

Availability of these issues increases the risk of this infection. Hyperglycemia damages a majority of functions monocytes and neutrophils [5]. It is much vital in restricting the invasion by pyogenic as well as other bacteria. The migration of phagocytic cells to the location of infection is generally damaged in

the patients of diabetes mellitus but is improves with the better glycemic control [6]. The main rationale of this research work was to examine the clinical presentation of patients of pneumonia present with Diabetes Mellitus, to investigate the frequent etiological agents responsible for pneumonia in patients of Diabetes Mellitus and to examine the outcome of pneumonia in the patients of Diabetes Mellitus.

METHDOLOGY:

40 patients of Diabetes Mellitus suffering from pneumonia were the part of this study and the duration of this study was from June 2019 to May 2020. We obtained the detailed history from all the patients. We also performed the systemic examination of all participants of this research work. Various bio-chemical parameters as FBS, CBC, RFT, ESR, PPBS, SGPT, HbA1c, serum electrolyte, fundus investigation, urine routine X-ray of chest and kidney's ultrasonography were observed in all the patients according to radiological and clinical presentation. We used the criteria of ADA (American Diabetes Association) for the diagnosis of Diabetes Mellitus. we diagnosed pneumonia with the help of X-ray of chest and associated symptoms. We performed the follow-up on the basis of improvement of symptoms and with the repetition of radiograph of chest.

RESULTS:

64% patients were male and 36% patients were females in this research work (Table 1).

Table-1: Age & Gender Distribution

Characteristics		No. of patients	%
Gender	Male	22	64
	Female	18	36
Age (Years)	15-39	5	14
	40-64	29	62
	> 65	6	24

In this current research work, majority of the patients were having 40 to 64 years of age with a mean age of 52.50 years. As presented in Table-2, most of the patients of this research work were present with Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus.

Table- 2: Type of Diabetes HbA1c Level

Characteristics		No. of patients	%
Type of Diabetes	Type 1 DM	7	10
	Type 2 DM	33	90
HbA1c Level	< 7	0	-
	> 7 to < 8	6	8
	> 8 to < 9	14	42
	> 9	20	50

Most of the patients were present with uncontrolled diabetes as level of HbA1c was higher than 7. As stated in Table-3, approximately 48.0% patients were present with comorbid complication.

Table-3: Concomitant Diseases

Diseases	No. of patients	%
Hypertension	10	24
COPD	8	20
IHD	6	16
Others	1	6

There was existence of multiple co-morbidities in 20.0% patients. Most prominent symptoms as noted in this research work were high temperature, cough, dyspnea and anorexia. Most of the patients of this research work were also suffering from tuberculosis.

Table-4: Predominant Symptoms and Radiological Features

Symptoms and Radiological Features	N	%
Fever	38	80
Cough with or without expectoration	46	96
Chest pain	15	34
Symptoms Anorexia	29	62
Dyspnoea	32	68
Weight Loss	13	30
Other complain	6	16
Radiological Multilobar involvement with cavity & fibrosis	22	48
Features Pleural effusion	10	24

Most common reason of pneumonia in this current research work was infection of tuberculous followed by Strep. Spp. In this current research work, there was presence of poly-microbial infection in 10% patients. In current research work, there was presence of involvement of multi lobes with fibrosis and cavity in 48.0% patients. The rate of mortality in this research work was 8.0%.

Table-5: Common Causative Organism

Diseases	N	%
AFB	14	32
Strept. Spp.	13	30
Klebsiella & Other gram negative	1	6
Atypical & fungal	7	18
Polymicrobial	5	10

DISCUSSION:

There is dominance of male diabetic patients suffering from pneumonia. Miquel [4] in his research work also stated that most of the patients suffering from diabetes were males (60.0%). Jette [8] stated that 56% patients were males and 44% patients were females in his research work. Akbar DH also stated the dominance of male gender [7]. The reason behind the dominance of the male gender is more exposure to the outdoor activities, stress and availability of the atherosclerosis regardless of various genetic factors. Jette [8] examined that 78.0% patients were present with more than 65 years of age with an average age of 62 years. Most possible reason of the most of the adult patients in this current research work is because of

genetic susceptibility, there is high risk of acquiring Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus in region and they develop this complication at very early age as compared to the other races in the world. Jette [8] also reported in his research work that most of the patients of his study were present with Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus (93.0%).

Jette also stated that 13.0% patients were present with HbA1c level higher than 9 and 26.0% patients were present with HbA1c level lower than 7. Possible causes for uncontrolled Diabetes Mellitus in this current research work which was conducted among the lower class were unawareness, education lack, not following the guidelines about diet, modification about lifestyle, physical activities and appropriate medication. Miquel [4] stated that

56.0% patients were present with coexisting disease along with Diabetes Mellitus. Spomenka [13] described frequent causes of pneumonia in the patients of diabetes as *Strep. Spp.*, fungal infection, staphylococcus and gram-negative organisms. Eirini [3] stated that common micro-organism in the patients of diabetes as *Strep. Spp.*, fungal infection, *Klebsiella* and *E. coli*. In research work conducted in Congo, it was concluded that there is aggravating impact of diabetes on tuberculosis. There was much common prevalence of tuberculosis in the patients of diabetes. This leads to highly pronounced radiological symptoms, failure of treatment and high rate of mortality in these patients [10]. Miquel [9] stated that there was presence of poly-microbial infection in 9.0% patients. Miquel did not include the tubercular pneumonia in his research work.

Cause for the high amount of the tubercular infection in this current research work is the high incidence of the tuberculosis in the population on which this research work was performed. Because of overcrowding in our region, patients of diabetes are highly prone to acquire this infection due to high vulnerability. Hyperglycemia supports the propagation, viability and growth of tubercle bacilli. Prevalence of TB in the patients of Diabetes Mellitus was 3 or 4 times higher as compared to normal general population [9]. Prabhakar [11] stated the multi-lobar involvement in approximately 50.0% patients. In the patients of diabetes present with pneumonia, there is association of diabetes with the involvement of multiple lobes as well as poly-microbial etiology.

Hyperglycemia is cause of impairment of high amount of functions in neutrophils & macrophages, it is vital for restricting invasion by bacteria so due to weakened immunity chances of multiple lobes rises. TB in the patients of Diabetes Mellitus has association with wide caseation of tissue of lung and cavitory abrasion with less involvement of pleural [3]. High rate of mortality in these patients was because of adverse control of diabetes, related comorbid complications, and presence of high risk for septicemia & bacteremia. Miquel [12] stated 17.0% rate of mortality which is much higher. Possible reason of the high rate of mortality in this current research work was younger age group which is the indication of better immunity. One other important reason for low rate of mortality in this research work was that most of the patients were present with score 1 or 0 according to criteria of CURB-65 [13] which is used for the detection of prognosis of the patients present with pneumonia.

CONCLUSION:

In these patients, there is significant influence of the adverse Diabetes Mellitus control, availability of comorbid complications and risk of bacteremia and

septicemia on the rate of mortality in these patients. Better glycemic control, in time treatment in accordance with the sensitivity of the report, balanced diet and related treatment can improve the adverse outcome of pneumonia in the patients present with Diabetes Mellitus.

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